

Iconological Analysis of the Tomb of Tutankhamun

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Introduction

The tomb of Tutankhamun, also known as KV62, is one of the most famous discoveries from ancient Egypt. The tomb contains richly decorated wall paintings that, although modest in size, present an intriguing view of Egyptian conceptions about the afterlife and the role of the pharaoh in this eternal life. The decorations on the walls, including depictions of rituals and mythical journeys, contain symbolism that emphasizes both the pharaoh's power and his divine status while also guiding his transition to the afterlife.

The paintings in KV62 differ in style and structure from those in other royal tombs from the same period. While many tombs emphasize a continuous cycle of rebirth, the decorations in KV62 instead depict a linear transition from life to death, presumably influenced by the religious reforms of Tutankhamun's predecessor, Akhenaten. This unique combination of traditional and renewed symbolism reflects not only a personal interpretation of the afterlife but also possibly the complex religious changes during the late 18th Dynasty. On the northern wall, we even find traces that may indicate an earlier, alternative purpose for the tomb. Nicholas Reeves, for instance, suggests in his hypothesis that this wall was originally intended for a female ruler, probably Nefertiti.

This analysis offers an extensive iconological interpretation of the paintings on the walls of KV62, highlighting both the traditional and innovative aspects. Emphasis is placed on the symbolism, rituals, and artistic style features that distinguish Tutankhamun's tomb, giving it a special place in Egyptian tomb art and religion.

East Wall

Tutankhamun rests on a funerary bed, a scarab pendant visible on his chest.

The pharaoh wears a floral wreath around his neck. His mummy rests on a lion-shaped funerary bed.

The scarab pendant on Tutankhamun's chest and the lion-shaped funerary bed are potent symbols. The scarab, associated with Khepri, the rising sun, reinforces the theme of regeneration, linking Tutankhamun with cosmic rebirth. The lion-shaped bed, a common feature in royal funerary iconography, underscores his royal power, symbolically combining both temporal authority and divine renewal.

The mummy on the funerary bed, is placed under two canopies, one nested within the other. Between the poles of the inner canopy hang two garlands of flowers. The poles of the inner canopy are decorated, unlike those of the outer canopy, which bear only two red-and-white streamers at the top. Both canopies are adorned with an architrave from which clusters of grapes hang.

The nested canopies over the bier elaborately adorned with floral garlands and clusters of grapes, are potent emblems of renewal and abundance. The floral wreath around the mummy's neck echoes the Egyptian funerary tradition, linking Tutankhamun with both mortuary ritual and divine favor. The garlands of grapes draw on the ancient Egyptian symbolism of eternal sustenance in the afterlife, adding layers of meaning that situate Tutankhamun in an idealized, abundant afterlife.

Above this hangs a cavetto cornice and a frieze of uraei (cobras) holding the solar disk. The uraei holding the solar disk signify divine protection, the presence of the goddess Wadjet, and association with the sun god Re. In this context, the uraei emphasize Tutankhamun's assimilation into the divine protection and his connection with the solar deity, further preparing him for his journey to the afterlife.

The funerary platform beneath the canopies is mounted on a boat. Red-and-white streamers, commonly used to decorate temples during festivals, are fastened to the boat's ends. Steering oars, representing Horus, terminate in falcon heads at the prow, while an eye on the boat's bow symbolizes the sun god Re, who perceives all.

The falcon and eye symbols on the boat are closely tied to Re's journey across the heavens and through the underworld, reinforcing Tutankhamun's alignment with the daily solar cycle and the dual barks of day and night (mandjet and mesketet). This visual association affirms Tutankhamun's journey through the Duat, with Re as his guide and protector, ensuring his transition to eternal life.

A royal sphinx stands on a wooden pedestal at the boat's bow, which likely signifies that the catafalque is part of a royal procession.

On either side of the canopies stand Isis and Nephthys with their hands raised. They are dressed in white robes and wear a head scarf, representing "Mistress of the House". The depiction of Isis and Nephthys flanking the bier, hands raised in protective gestures, symbolizes their role as guardians of the deceased pharaoh, echoing their mythological protection of Osiris. The goddesses' "Mistress of the House" titles

reference their ancient roles as protectors of the king's body and his ka, with Isis specifically bearing the hieroglyph for "throne," emphasizing her status as the throne's divine protector.

The canopies and boat rest on a sled. The sled is a fairly primitive means of transportation, used by the Egyptians to move objects over land.

The sled is symbolic of movement and transition, serving as a vehicle that physically conveys the pharaoh's body from the realm of the living to the threshold of the afterlife. In Egyptian beliefs, the sled functions as a metaphor for the deceased's journey across realms, indicating Tutankhamun's progression from earthly existence to a divine, eternal state. The sled can be linked to Osiris's funerary myth, where the god's body was conveyed to his tomb by his followers, Isis and Nephthys. In this way, the sled aligns Tutankhamun's journey with that of Osiris, reinforcing his identity as a resurrected god-king. This alignment with Osiris is strengthened by the presence of Isis and Nephthys on either side, raising their hands in a protective gesture.

The sled is pulled by 12 people, of which nine presumably represent the "Nine Friends of the King." Behind them are the two viziers of the South and the North, distinguishable by their official attire. Both wear the same sleeveless white garment, reaching just below the armpits, held up by two straps fastened behind the neck. It is clear in the depiction that the artist initially drew two figures with the same attire as the other ten, with covered shoulders. This can be seen on the right vizier, where the outline of the garment at the neck is visible but ultimately not painted over. The heads are shaven, as was customary for their office. Viziers sometimes also served as High Priests, and for priests, it was customary to be shaved as a sign of purity.

This gathering reflects Tutankhamun's royal entourage, symbolizing loyalty and connection to the earthly administration, while also serving as a symbolic link to the king's rebirth in the Duat. The inclusion of these figures in royal attire and specific

postures aligns with New Kingdom funerary practices, marking his journey as both royal and divine.

The identity of the last man, who stands behind the group of nine and is dressed in a transparent garment reaching just below the knee with a gathered apron tied at the waist, is unclear. This attire was very popular at the end of the 18th Dynasty. He also wears a wig. Like the viziers, he wears a white headband, which Howard Carter noted was often depicted in funerary processions in private tombs and is still worn by family members in Egypt today. All of them wear white sandals, two pairs of which were found in the tomb.

The white color of the clothing undoubtedly also relates to the funeral, although it was common for high officials and dignitaries to wear white attire, while ordinary people wore more colorful clothing. The heads of the twelve men are somewhat symmetrically painted next to each other. Interestingly, the hands posed some difficulty; the first person pulling the sled has both hands on the rope, as do the front vizier and his predecessor, who stand close to the rope. The vizier and predecessor beside them both have no hands on the rope. The front seven men each have one hand on the rope, except for the last in this group, who stands closest to the rope and has two hands on it again. There is no sense of perspective at the feet. The feet are nearly always arranged next to each other in a row, left-right foot... it does not matter. Oddly, the first man pulling the sled has a 'left foot.' This foot shows all five toes with toenails, while for all other feet, the toes and toenails are not visible, meaning they are right feet.

Usually, in depictions, the feet were painted with only the inner side visible, that is, without toes, so only the big toe is visible. Three of the twenty-one figures painted on the walls of the burial chamber have a foot with five visible toenails!

The details of the depiction of realistic toes and the arrangement of the figures, likely show residual influence from the Amarna period. In this period, during Akhenaten's rule, the pharaoh was depicted more realistically. This stylistic remnant suggests that while Tutankhamun's tomb adopted traditional Theban iconography, it also retained elements from the preceding era, creating a blend of innovation and orthodoxy that speaks to the complexity of his reign.

The images on this wall depict part of Tutankhamun's funeral. Tutankhamun himself lies on a bier under a double canopy and is pulled on a sled by a group of twelve people, all wearing a white mourning band. This depiction of a funeral is standard in Egyptian private tombs. Since the Middle Kingdom, they have been found in many private tomb chapels. It was not until the New Kingdom, in the 18th Dynasty, that they became more common (Tomb of Ramose no. 55, Tomb of Userkhat no. 56). Tutankhamun is one of the first pharaohs to have such a depiction in his tomb. Such a visual scene is very unusual for a royal tomb. This is likely due to the changes made by his predecessor Amenhotep IV/Akhenaten, who also had many ordinary scenes from daily life depicted on the temple.

The east wall suggests a deeper layer of symbolic meaning. The depiction of Tutankhamun's funeral procession highlights unique elements reserved for pharaohs. The east wall imagery reinforces Tutankhamun's divine role in death, aligning him with Osirian tradition and asserting his journey to eternal life as an exceptional event beyond that of ordinary mortals.

Funerary Procession of Tutankhamun

After the prescribed 70-day embalming process, Tutankhamun's mummy, adorned with a funerary collar and regalia, was placed beneath a double canopy on a ceremonial bark set atop a sled. This arrangement, incorporating elements of both terrestrial and celestial symbolism, underscored the king's divine status and his liminal position between worlds. The sled, an ancient mode of transport in ritual contexts, likely symbolized his transition from the mortal realm to the Duat.

The procession began on land, led by red oxen—a color symbolically associated with strength and vitality—drawing the sled toward the Nile. There, the pharaoh's body was transferred to boats for a private, symbolic passage along the river. This transition to water resonated with Osirian iconography, marking the Nile as a passage between life and death, linking Tutankhamun's journey to the regenerative power of Osiris.

Upon docking near the mortuary temple, close to his tomb in the Valley of the Kings, priests conducted the final rites over four days to ensure Tutankhamun's transformation into a divine entity. Ay, acting as setem priest, dressed in leopard skin and a blue helmet, presided over the ceremonies, symbolizing his authority in overseeing the pharaoh's apotheosis.

For the final journey to the tomb, the red oxen were replaced by human attendants, including the "Nine Friends of the King." This group, a symbolic assembly of high officials, represented the king's personal council and loyalty, embodying a continuation

of his earthly retinue. Behind them, the viziers of Upper and Lower Egypt, identifiable by their white garments and shaven heads, emphasized the unified power of the Two Lands even in death.

An unidentified figure appears behind the viziers, dressed similarly yet without distinguishing symbols, leaving his role in the procession open to interpretation, possibly as a ritual or honorary presence.

This richly symbolic procession synthesizes royal and Osirian iconography, framing Tutankhamun's journey as one of divine transformation. Figures like Ay and the "Nine Friends" reinforce the king's transition into the eternal cycle of divine kingship, aligning his path with Osiris's own mythic journey.

North Wall

The first scene, directly adjoining the east wall, shows Tutankhamun before the new pharaoh, his successor Ay, who performs the "Opening of the Mouth" ritual, a ceremony intended to restore the mummy's ability to speak, to eat and drink, and to move within the underworld.

This was one of the last funeral ceremonies and aimed to reawaken the body. Ay is depicted as 'setem' priest of Ptah. As was customary for a priest during this ceremony, Ay wears a leopard skin. He holds the liturgical adze in both hands. By touching the mouth and eyes with it, they would open for eternal life.

In no other tomb is the successor of the deceased pharaoh depicted, making this depiction unique! This image is therefore one of the most famous and is often found in books. Tutankhamun, next to Ay, is depicted in mummy form as Osiris with the usual attributes: the ostrich feather headdress, flails, and divine beard. He has become Osiris

and thus also the (symbolic) father of Ay, for as we know from the Osiris myth, the pharaoh was seen as the "embodiment" of Horus on earth and son of Osiris.

The middle scene shows Tutankhamun before the goddess Nut. Tutankhamun is depicted in the same posture as the two life-sized statues that stood at the entrance of the burial chamber, as a kind of guards. In one hand they hold a club, and in the other hand a staff. They are probably ritual objects. The statues were blackened because they represented the Nile mud that flooded and gave it fertility every year. Black signified resurrection and the continuity of life. The statues bear inscriptions stating that they are royal Kas. The function of these statues was to provide Tutankhamun's Ka with a body in which it could reside. Staff and club likely indicate the pharaoh's status and only have symbolic meaning. In his left hand, Tutankhamun also holds the 'ankh' symbol, the symbol for 'life.'

The pharaoh stands before the goddess Nut, mother of Osiris, the deceased king. Nut is the first deity the deceased pharaoh encounters. We also see this in the 18th Dynasty. In the lid of many coffins from that time, the goddess Nut is depicted life-sized with open arms. Nut is the goddess of the sky. She is the sky through which the pharaoh will travel. The goddess Nut, therefore, marks the beginning of his journey to the underworld.

Nut performs 'nini' (sprinkling her hands with water in greeting) and holds the hieroglyph for 'water' in each hand.

The last scene shows Tutankhamun greeting Osiris by embracing him. This time it is Osiris himself, not Tutankhamun in the guise of Osiris. Osiris' skin is darker in color, green, undoubtedly to indicate that he is a corpse. Tutankhamun wears the striped

nemes headdress. Behind him stands his Ka counterpart. Every pharaoh had a twin brother, his Ka, who was stillborn and immediately disappeared into the underworld. In contrast to that of ordinary people, the pharaoh's Ka is a god with divine powers. He also wears a divine beard and a loincloth and belt in which gods were often depicted (for example, on the west and south walls). The Ka of the king was not only the pharaoh's vital force but also a god. He had to protect the pharaoh in the underworld. The Ka bears the 'Ka' symbol on his head, two raised hands between which the so-called Horus name, which represents the pharaoh most as a deity: 'strong bull.'

Above it is the royal uraeus, the cobra, and a falcon, also representing Horus. The Ka has placed his right hand brotherly around Tutankhamun. In his left hand, he holds the 'ankh' symbol, the symbol for 'life.' In this scene, the pharaoh, with his Ka, his double and divine power, is welcomed in the underworld by Osiris, 'the first of the West.' His journey through the underworld, the West (where the sun sets), is addressed on the adjacent west wall.

The north wall's scenes underscore Tutankhamun's transformation into Osiris, a rite that aligns the pharaoh with the god's promise of eternal life. This transformation emphasizes Tutankhamun's dual role as both a human king and divine protector of Egypt, linking his death and rebirth with Osiris' own.

Nicholas Reeves offers an alternative interpretation for the scenes and characters depicted on the north wall of the tomb. Reeves suggests that the north wall may have originally been intended for the burial of a female pharaoh, probably Nefertiti, and was later adapted for Tutankhamun. He identifies several key differences and modifications that indicate that the tomb was initially designed for a female ruler and was only later converted into Tutankhamun's burial chamber.

- **Identity and Role of the Characters:** Where Ay currently serves as the priest during the 'Opening of the Mouth' ritual for Tutankhamun, Reeves suggests that this scene was originally intended to depict the young Tutankhamun himself as a priest, while the mummy represented Nefertiti. According to Reeves, there are visual features in the depicted faces that indicate an earlier phase in which Tutankhamun was portrayed as a child and Nefertiti as the mummy, after which the iconography was later adapted to the new pharaoh and his successor.

- Decoration Phases:** According to Reeves, the decorations on the north wall were applied in two phases. He attributes the first phase to a female pharaoh from the Amarna period, characterized by the application of a gray underlayer and an earlier, Amarna-style proportion division of 20 squares instead of the later 18 squares used for Tutankhamun. In the second phase, yellow paint and new details were added to adapt the scenes to Tutankhamun's funeral.

- Ka Figure:** The Ka figure behind Tutankhamun displays visual features that align more with female depictions from the Amarna period, suggesting that the Ka figure was originally an image of Nefertiti. This figure would only later have been

provided with the Ka symbol and corresponding attributes to adapt it to Tutankhamun's iconography.

- **Nut as Guide:** Where Nut is depicted as the goddess welcoming and protecting Tutankhamun during his journey to the afterlife, Reeves suspects that this scene originally portrayed Nefertiti as the central figure. He suggests that Nut played a role in confirming Nefertiti's royal status as a female pharaoh, and that the iconography may have been later adjusted to fit Tutankhamun's funeral ritual.
- **Adaptations and Stylistic Differences:** Reeves emphasizes that the north wall deviates from the other walls in the burial chamber, both in the underlayer and in the colors and techniques used. Where the north wall exhibits unique features, such as a gray preparation layer and specific details in pigment use, this suggests, according to him, the possibility that the original decoration was made for another pharaoh from an earlier period, likely Nefertiti, before the tomb was allocated to Tutankhamun.
- **Reinterpretation of Symbols and Attributes:** Reeves suspects that many of the icons and attributes, such as facial features, clothing type, and divine insignia, were painted over or added during the second decoration phase. In his analysis, certain parts of the original decoration were modified or edited to better fit Tutankhamun's royal iconography, while many visual elements still refer to the Amarna style and the female pharaoh for whom the chamber was originally intended.
- Reeves' analysis adds an interesting dimension to the current interpretation of the north wall. It provides new perspectives on the possibility of an earlier burial in KV62 and the art historical adjustments that made the tomb suitable for Tutankhamun.

West Wall

The west wall of Tutankhamun's tomb (KV62) features a partial depiction of the Amduat, an essential funerary text that narrates the sun god Re's journey through the Duat—the underworld—over the twelve hours of the night. In Egyptian cosmology, this journey was crucial, as Re encountered various beings, navigated challenges, and underwent transformations that enabled his rebirth at dawn. The Amduat, therefore, not only symbolizes Re's daily regeneration but also serves as a broader metaphor for cosmic order, or *ma'at*, which ensures the stability and renewal of the universe. By narrating Re's struggle against forces that would attempt to disrupt his passage, the Amduat emphasizes the protective roles of accompanying deities who ward off chaos and safeguard his nightly progress. The scene on the west wall, though selective, captures key elements of this journey and directly connects Tutankhamun's own passage into eternity with the universal cycle of death and rebirth.

In KV62, the painting on the west wall condenses the first hour of the Amduat into three horizontal registers, in line with the structure of each of the twelve hours, which are divided similarly in the full text. The middle register shows Re aboard the solar bark, moving toward the eastern horizon, where he will emerge reborn as the morning sun. This journey on the bark situates Re within a cyclical process, navigating from the light of day into the realms of night and death before returning. The two outer registers contain "god tables," listing various deities assigned to guard, assist, or empower Re during each of the twelve hours of his journey. Originally, the Amduat contains tables

listing 84 gods across these registers, each with a specific role in Re's journey. In KV62, however, only the initial two gods of each row are represented, a stylistic simplification that maintains ritual significance without reproducing the full pantheon. This selective depiction conveys that, despite the abridged arrangement, Re's journey remains stable and divinely guided.

At the top right of the west wall, a framed grouping of five gods forms part of the divine crew that accompanies Re on his solar bark through the Duat. This crew is responsible for securing Re's passage through each hour and safeguarding him from chaotic forces. Their protective presence ensures that the journey maintains ma'at, the cosmic order needed for the sun god's eventual rebirth. Below are their names, presented from right to left, with hieroglyphic transcription and translation:

m;t (Maat): The goddess of justice and cosmic order, Maat embodies the principle of ma'at, fundamental to Egyptian religion and governance. Since the Old Kingdom, Maat has been integral to the final judgment of the dead, symbolizing truth and balance in the presence of Osiris. Here, her role underscores the need for cosmic balance within the Duat and ensures that Re's journey adheres to ma'at, reflecting the stability necessary for his eventual rebirth.

nb.twj; (Mistress of the Solar Bark): Known as Hathor, this goddess is described as the "House of Horus" and presides over the West as the protector of the deceased. Her role as Mistress of the Solar Bark reflects her dual function as both a nurturing deity and a guide within the underworld, enabling Re's passage through the realms of death.

hr (Horus): Represented as the son of Osiris and the "father" of pharaohs, Horus symbolizes divine kingship and serves as a link between the mortal pharaoh and the gods. His presence here emphasizes the protective aspect of divine kingship, securing Re's journey and, symbolically, supporting the pharaoh's own journey toward eternal life.

k;sj; (Kashu): Often depicted as the leader of the solar bark, Kashu guides Re's vessel through the challenges of the Duat, ensuring the path remains clear. As a divine

helmsman, his role is essential in maintaining the steady movement of Re's bark, preventing disruptions in the journey.

nhs (Nehes): Known as the 'lookout' god, Nehes occupies a position on the bark where he can anticipate and guard against any threats to Re's passage. As a vigilant watcher, Nehes' role is crucial in navigating the dangerous waters of the Duat and aligns with the broader theme of protection and foresight.

Together, these gods form a partial crew that exemplifies the roles necessary to secure Re's journey. The full crew would traditionally comprise eight gods and goddesses, reflecting a more extensive divine entourage supporting the sun god's regeneration.

On the upper left of the west wall, the Khepri bark appears, with Re depicted as a scarab beetle. Khepri, as a scarab, represents the solar god's potential for regeneration. Egyptians observed the scarab's behavior, particularly its egg-laying habits within dung balls, as a form of spontaneous creation, making it an ideal symbol for the god's power to renew himself. By depicting Re as a scarab, the tomb's iconography underscores this theme of self-generation—a central concept in his nightly transformation and daily rebirth.

The Eye of Re is also depicted on the prow of the solar bark, a protective and vigilant symbol stemming from an Old Kingdom myth where Re sent his eye to earth to prevent insurrection among its inhabitants. Here, the eye on the prow signifies Re's omniscience and his authority over chaotic forces, reinforcing his journey's alignment with cosmic order. Traditionally, the two eyes of Re symbolize the barks of day (right eye) and night (left eye), emphasizing the dual nature of his passage and his continuous protection across the realms.

The twelve baboons depicted in reverence toward the solar bark on the west wall serve as both protectors and devotees. Sacred to Thoth, the god of wisdom, baboons were associated with dawn worship due to their observed behaviors at sunrise, which the Egyptians perceived as acts of homage to Re. Positioned in the first hour of the Amduat, these baboons not only greet Re as he enters the Duat but also function as apotropaic figures, countering threats to his journey. Their inclusion serves to reinforce ma'at, symbolizing the cosmic stability they uphold as they prepare the way for Re's rebirth. This alignment with ma'at serves not only the sun god but also extends to Tutankhamun, stabilizing the liminal space between life and death, and facilitating the pharaoh's own transition into eternity.

The twelve baboons and the divine entourage on the west wall integrate Tutankhamun's passage with the solar deity's cyclical regeneration. By embodying both worship and protection, the baboons ensure Re's rebirth and, by extension, support Tutankhamun's entrance into the eternal cosmic cycle. Tutankhamun's alignment with Re's nightly journey thus signifies his own transformation, grounding him within the established order of divine kingship and the regenerative powers of the cosmos.

The iconography on the west wall, with its selective depiction of the Amduat, emphasizes divine guardianship, cosmic balance, and regeneration within the royal tomb context. The twelve baboons, protective deities, and the scarab symbol of Khepri encapsulate a theological vision in which Tutankhamun's afterlife is secured through his alignment with Re's continuous journey. This arrangement positions Tutankhamun within the eternal cycle of ma'at, underscoring his divine kingship through his es both

South Wall

On the right, Tutankhamun stands next to the goddess Hathor. She was, among other things, goddess of the West, protector of the Theban necropolis. She greeted the dead as they entered the underworld. On the wall, she gives life to Tutankhamun's nostrils by holding the 'ankh' symbol of 'life' near his nose. In her left hand, she holds a second 'ankh' symbol. In her white headband is the symbol of the West. Hathor was sometimes also seen as the mother of Horus (the pharaoh), and her name can be interpreted as "house of Horus". She was very popular during the 18th and 19th Dynasties and was often depicted alongside pharaohs in tombs and temples.

Tutankhamun stands in a solemn posture, as a pharaoh was often depicted when approaching a temple, with his palms turned backward. He wears the same loincloth as in the scene on the north wall with his Ka. He also wears sandals, like Ay on the north wall and the people pulling the sled on the east wall. On his head is the funerary headdress Khat, a veil tied at the nape of the neck, just like Isis and Nephthys on the east wall. This is strange because on the other walls, only living persons, people present at the funeral, wear white sandals. It is also strange that Tutankhamun himself also wears a funerary headdress here. The meaning of this is unclear. Could he be alive

again and attending his own funeral? Tutankhamun, like most people on the north and south walls, wears a collar necklace. According to the Egyptians, the collar possessed magical power against hostile forces. Although usually made of faience and sometimes of gold, during funeral meals, they were made of natural materials like flowers and leaves.

Behind Tutankhamun stands Anubis with the jackal head, god of mummification. He opened the way to the underworld. In the Osiris myth, his mother Nephthys abandoned him, and Isis raised him. It was he who embalmed Osiris's body. Anubis also brought the dead before the judges, for whom he weighed the heart of the dead, the seat of the 'conscience.' The judges would determine whether the pharaoh had committed no sins in his life. If he was found innocent, Tutankhamun would "live forever." Anubis has placed his left hand on Tutankhamun's shoulder, as if leading him to Hathor. In his right hand, he holds the 'ankh' symbol. Anubis' right foot again shows an Amarna trait: the toes, which were previously discussed regarding the Group of Nine on the east wall.

During the discovery of Tutankhamun's tomb in 1922 by Howard Carter, a portion of the South wall was removed to provide access to the tomb. The current location of this removed section remains unknown, but its appearance is preserved through black-and-white photographs taken by Harry Burton, which capture this part of the South wall.

On this portion of the wall Isis stands behind Anubis in a greeting posture, like the goddess Nut on the north wall. Isis was the mother of Horus and foster mother of Anubis. Just as she protected Osiris's body and aided Horus in the struggle against Seth, so would she help Tutankhamun. On her head is the emblem associated with her: the throne of Osiris. Three "gods of the underworld" are crouched behind her,

concluding the paintings. It is not clear whether they only serve as an ending or also have a specific meaning. Their captions only mention their names and do not clarify their function.

Above all the paintings on the walls is a dark blue strip painted in the shape of the hieroglyphic sign for 'sky.' Very appropriate. This usage is very old. In the tomb of Amenhotep II, these stripes appear in the shape of the hieroglyph for 'sky' above the images where the pharaoh is depicted before various gods. Above the complete versions of the *Amduat* in the tombs of Thutmose III and Amenhotep II, they are also present. The ceilings are also painted full of stars. They symbolize the night sky through which the pharaoh travels. Only at the beginning on the east wall and the end on the south wall are these 'sky signs' connected with the horizontal lines at the bottom of the painting.

Closing Interpretation

In KV62, the tomb of Tutankhamun, the iconographic program presents an intricate fusion of traditional motifs and novel adaptations that underscore the pharaoh's transition to the afterlife and his divinized status. Unlike other royal tombs that predominantly emphasize cyclical rebirth, KV62 reveals a more linear trajectory, which may reflect theological developments characteristic of Akhenaten's reign. This linearity reconfigures Tutankhamun's journey as a directional passage from life through death to divine rebirth, aligning him with both Osirian and solar cultic traditions.

The east wall offers a striking portrayal of Tutankhamun reclining on a lion-shaped funerary bed, flanked by attendants and surrounded by symbolic regalia that emphasize his sacralized journey. The sled carrying his bier toward eternity invokes Osirian resurrection motifs, situating Tutankhamun as a god-king within a mythological tradition of death and rebirth. This iconography reinforces the Osirian dimension of his divine identity and situates the east wall as a symbolic threshold to eternity.

On the north wall, the depiction of Ay performing the "Opening of the Mouth" ritual positions Ay as Horus to Tutankhamun's Osiris, visually enacting the king's transformation into a divinized being. Nicholas Reeves' hypothesis that KV62 may have originally been designed for Nefertiti gains support from stylistic and material variances in the wall's decorative phases, suggesting an adaptation process tailored to its eventual occupant. Reeves' perspective illuminates the flexibility of royal tomb design and iconography during the late 18th Dynasty, particularly under the theological shifts introduced by Akhenaten. If KV62 was repurposed for Tutankhamun, this fluidity not only reflects the religious and political transitions of the time but also underscores KV62's significance as an artifact reflecting the period's evolving royal and divine ideologies.

The west wall depicts a partial Amduat scene, situating Tutankhamun within the cosmic cycle of Re's nocturnal journey through the Duat. Here, the twelve baboons, Re's divine entourage, and Khepri as the scarab-headed sun god emphasize the king's association with solar regeneration. This narrative thread aligns Tutankhamun's afterlife with Re's own renewal, placing him firmly within the perpetual order of ma'at and reinforcing his role as a cosmic stabilizer.

The south wall completes the visual program, portraying Hathor and Anubis guiding Tutankhamun into the western realm, symbolizing his formal entry into the divine sphere. Hathor's nurturing gesture and Anubis' guardianship underscore the pharaoh's transition under divine auspices, affirming his place among the gods.

KV62, in its entirety, serves as an extraordinary testament to royal ideology during a period of intense theological transformation, harmonizing cosmic and royal motifs to secure Tutankhamun's eternal role within the cosmic order. The tomb's iconography thus encapsulates a complex vision of kingship, divinity, and cosmology that continues to illuminate the spiritual and ideological landscape of the late 18th Dynasty.

Literature

All images are sourced from the Factum Foundation, <https://factumfoundation.org/>

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2. Reeves, Nicholas. *The Complete Tutankhamun: The King, the Tomb, the Royal Treasure*. London: Thames & Hudson, 1990.

This book provides an extensive analysis of the treasures in the tomb and discusses the iconography of the wall paintings and the symbolism of the tomb artifacts.

3. Hornung, Erik. *The Tomb of Pharaoh Tutankhamun*. New York: Cornell University Press, 1991.

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4. El Mahdy, Christine. *Tutankhamen: The Life and Death of a Pharaoh*. New York: St. Martin's Press, 1999.

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5. Eaton-Krauss, Marianne, and Erhart Graefe. *The Small Golden Shrine from the Tomb of Tutankhamun*. Oxford: Griffith Institute, 1985.

This book explores lesser-known aspects of Tutankhamun's life, reign, and burial, focusing on recent discoveries and scholarly interpretations. It provides fresh insights into the young pharaoh's historical and cultural significance beyond his famous tomb.

6. Weeks, Kent R. *Atlas of the Valley of the Kings. Study Edition*. Cairo: American University in Cairo Press, 2003.

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7. Porter Bertha and Moss Rosalind L.B., *Topographical Bibliography of Ancient Egyptian Hieroglyphic Texts, Reliefs, and Paintings I: The Theban Necropolis Part 2: Royal Tombs and Smaller Cemeteries*, Griffith Institute, Ashmolean Museum, Oxford, 1989, 569-586.

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8. Hornung, Erik. *The Valley of the Kings: Horizon of Eternity*. New York: Timken Publishers, 1990.

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9. Assmann, Jan. *Egyptian Solar Religion in the New Kingdom: Re, Amun, and the Crisis of Polytheism*. London: Routledge, 1995.

This book delves into the sun god Re and the role of solar iconography in New Kingdom tombs, including Tutankhamun's.

10. Assmann, Jan. *Death and Salvation in Ancient Egypt*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2005.

This work examines ancient Egyptian beliefs about death, the afterlife, and the journey of the soul. It explores concepts of immortality, funerary

practices, and the theological frameworks that shaped Egyptian views on salvation and the afterlife.

11. Hartwig, Melinda K. *A Companion to Ancient Egyptian Art*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2015.

This comprehensive guide includes a section on iconography in royal tombs, covering the visual symbols and ritual depictions seen in Tutankhamun's tomb.

12. Wilkinson, Richard H. *The Complete Gods and Goddesses of Ancient Egypt*. London: Thames & Hudson, 2003.

An in-depth analysis of gods and their iconography, many of whom appear on the walls of Tutankhamun's tomb.

13. Willems, Harco (ed.). *Social Aspects of Funerary Culture in the Egyptian Old and Middle Kingdoms*. Leuven: Peeters Publishers, 2001.

Although focused on earlier periods, this book provides insights into the development of iconographic traditions and symbols that continued into the New Kingdom.

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14. Hornung, Erik. *The Ancient Egyptian Books of the Afterlife*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1999.

A comprehensive study of Egyptian books of the dead, including the *Amduat*, which appears on the west wall of Tutankhamun's tomb.

15. Hornung, Erik. *The Tomb of Pharaoh Seti I*. Zürich: Artemis, 1991.

Although focused on the tomb of Seti I, this book provides valuable insights into the iconography of royal tombs and its influence on later tombs, including that of Tutankhamun.

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16. Smith, Ray Winfield, and Donald B. Redford. *The Akhenaten Temple Project, I. Initial Discoveries*. Warminster: Aris and Phillips, 1976.

This publication presents the initial findings of the Akhenaten Temple Project, uncovering early insights into the architecture and artifacts of Akhenaten's temple at Karnak. It sheds light on the religious reforms and artistic innovations introduced during his reign.

17. Reeves, Nicholas & Wilkinson, Richard H. *The Complete Valley of the Kings: Tombs and Treasures of Egypt's Greatest Pharaohs*. London: Thames & Hudson, 1996.

Includes iconographic analyses of Amarna influences on tomb decoration, including that of Tutankhamun.

18. Reeves, Nicholas. *The Decorated North Wall in the Tomb of Tutankhamun (KV 62): The Burial of Nefertiti? II*. Amarna Royal Tombs Project, Valley of the Kings, Occasional Paper No. 3. London: Thames & Hudson, 2015.

This booklet explores the theory that the north wall of Tutankhamun's tomb may have originally depicted scenes related to Queen Nefertiti's burial. It examines archaeological evidence and iconographic clues suggesting that the tomb may have been repurposed for Tutankhamun.

19. Troy, Lana. *Patterns of Queenship in Ancient Egyptian Myth and History*. Uppsala: Uppsala University Press, 1986.

Discusses the influence of female rulers like Nefertiti on iconography and religious depictions, relevant given the hypothesis that parts of Tutankhamun's tomb were originally intended for Nefertiti.

20. Baines, John. *Visual and Written Culture in Ancient Egypt*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2007.

Baines discusses the relationship between visual art and written texts, offering insight into the function of iconography and inscriptions in Tutankhamun's tomb.

21. Dodson, Aidan. *Amarna Sunset: Nefertiti, Tutankhamun, Ay, Horemheb, and the Egyptian Counter-Reformation*. Cairo: The American University in Cairo Press, 2009.

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22. Robins, Gay. "The Iconography of Queen Nefertiti in the Post-Amarna Period." *The Journal of Egyptian Archaeology* 82 (1996): 41–54.

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25. Bell, Lanny. "Luxor Temple and the Cult of the Royal Ka." *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 44, no. 4 (1985): 251-294.

This article examines the relationship between Luxor Temple and the cult of the royal *Ka*, exploring how the temple's rituals and architecture

symbolized the pharaoh's divine essence. It provides insights into the religious and political significance of the royal *Ka* in ancient Egypt.

26. Haas-Dantes, Fabienne. "The Tomb of Tutankhamun. The North Wall: Meaning and Symbols." *Nile* 15 (2018): 31-43.

This article analyzes the symbolism and iconography of the North Wall in Tutankhamun's tomb. It delves into the meanings behind the wall's imagery, examining how it reflects the beliefs and religious practices of ancient Egypt.

27. Factum Arte. "Factum Arte's Work in the Tombs of Tutankhamun, Nefertari and Seti I." *Report for the Supreme Council of Antiquities*, March-May 2009.

This report details Factum Arte's preservation and digital documentation efforts in the tombs of Tutankhamun, Nefertari, and Seti I. It highlights the techniques used to create accurate facsimiles and support conservation, ensuring the tombs' protection for future generations.

28. Reeves, Nicholas. "Tutankhamun: Technical Innovation, New Data, and Unexpected Discoveries." *in*: Adam Lowe ed., *Selected Factum Foundation projects carried out between 2019 and 2023, with contributions from Nicolas Béliard, Giulia Fornaciari, Ferdinand Saumarez Smith, Otto Lowe, Jorge Cano, and Carlos Bayod*. Madrid: Factum Foundation, (2023) 123-125.

This article explores recent technological advancements and unexpected discoveries in the study of Tutankhamun's tomb, shedding light on its construction, artifacts, and preservation. Through contributions from multiple experts, it reveals new data and insights into the tomb's historical and cultural significance.